

The Relationship of Mother's Nutritional Knowledge and the Practice of Giving Complete ASI Food (MP-ASI) To Toddler Age 6-12 Months at Bpm Ernah South Cimahi Coffee Garden

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ABSTRACT

Malnutrition in children can be caused by the mother's attitude or behavior in inappropriate feeding practices. This occurs because mothers' knowledge and skills regarding food, nutrition and practices in feeding children are still low. This study aims to determine the relationship between maternal nutritional knowledge and the practice of giving MP-ASI to toddlers aged 6-12 months at BPM Ernah Kebon Kopi Cimahi. The type of research is descriptive analytic with a cross sectional approach, sampling using proportional sampling. The research sample was 69 mothers who had toddlers aged 6-12 months. Data on maternal nutritional knowledge and practice of providing MP-ASI were obtained by interview using a questionnaire that had been tested for validity and reliability. Analysis of the relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable using Chi Square. The level of nutritional knowledge of respondents was high at 46 people (66.7%) and the practice of providing MP-ASI was carried out well by 41 people (59.4%). The research results showed that there was a relationship between maternal nutritional knowledge and the practice of providing MP-ASI ($p < 0.05$). It is hoped that PBM Ernah Kebon Kopi Cimahi will be more active in providing information through outreach and counseling to cadres and the community, especially mothers with toddlers, about improving nutrition and skills in the practice of providing MP-ASI.

KEYWORDS: Knowledge, Practice of Giving MP-ASI, Nutrition

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BACKGROUND

One effort to improve children's health and nutrition to achieve optimal growth and development is to provide the best food for children under 2 years of age. Global Strategy for Infant and Young Child Feeding, WHO/UNICEF recommends four important things that must be done, namely; (1) giving breast milk (ASI) to the baby immediately within 30 minutes after the baby is born, (2) giving only breast milk (ASI) or exclusive breastfeeding from birth until the baby is 6 months old, (3) giving food Companion of breast milk (MP ASI) from the time the baby is 6 months – 24 months old, (4) Continuing breastfeeding until the child is 24 months old or more (Ministry of Health of the Republic of Indonesia, 2011).

MP-ASI is food given to babies who are 6 months old or more because breast milk no longer meets the baby's nutritional needs. The age of 6-12 months is a critical period and a very

important period for the growth of toddlers, because at that age children already need adequate MP-ASI both in terms of quantity and quality. If babies and children aged 6-12 months do not get enough nutrition from MP-ASI, this will result in growth disorders and malnutrition.

Growth disorders begin to occur in the first 4-6 months of a baby's life. Starting from the age of 6 months, growth disturbances begin to become apparent and reach their peak at the age of 11 months. Apart from that, the weaning period which starts at the age of 6-12 months is the basis for the child's ability to recognize and consume various types of food in the following period (Ministry of Health, 2014).

Malnutrition is one of the main health problems in society. More than 2/3 of under-five deaths are related to inappropriate feeding practices for toddlers (Semahegn, 2014). One of the causes of malnutrition in toddlers is the mother's attitude or behavior in inappropriate feeding

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practices. This occurs because mothers' knowledge and skills regarding food, nutrition and practices in feeding children are still low.

Based on a preliminary study conducted by researchers at BPM Ernah Kebon Kopi Cimahi, data was obtained that in March 2019, the results of the Toddler Weighing Month were 9.43% of toddlers suffering from malnutrition (WW/U <-2 Z-score), 25.30% of toddlers short (WW/U <-2 Z-score) and 3.23% of underweight toddlers (WW/U <-2 Z-score). The results of interviews with several mothers of toddlers and based on information from cadres, there are still many mothers of toddlers who give MP-ASI before the baby is 6 months old. Mother only provides food in the form of rice porridge without supplementing it with other nutritious food ingredients, such as animal side dishes and vegetables. There are still mothers of toddlers who only give food to toddlers in the form of vegetable soup without any protein sources. Apart from that, there is also a public opinion that nutrient-dense MP-ASI can only be made from animal source food ingredients which are relatively expensive.

Considering that the impact of inappropriate feeding on toddlers can result in malnutrition which is very detrimental to toddlers in the future, preventive and corrective efforts need to be carried out. Supported by the data above, the author wants to know the relationship between maternal nutritional knowledge and the practice of providing complementary breast milk (MP-ASI) to toddlers aged 6-12 months. The location chosen was PBM Ernah Cimahi coffee garden.

METHOD

This research design uses descriptive analytics with a cross sectional approach. The research sample was 69 mothers who had toddlers aged 6-12 months using proportional sampling technique. This research was carried out at BPM Ernah Kebon Kopi Cimahi. Time: The research was carried out in March 2019. Data were collected on maternal nutritional knowledge and the practice of giving MP-ASI by interviewing using a questionnaire that had been tested for validity and reliability. The univariate data analysis technique used for the knowledge and practice of giving MP-ASI variables was by calculating the percentage (%). Bivariate analysis in this study used the *Chi Square* test.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Nutritional Knowledge of Mothers of Toddlers Aged 6-12 Months BPM Ernah Cimahi Coffee Garden

Knowledge is the result of knowing and this occurs after people sense a particular object. Measuring knowledge can be done by interviews or questionnaires that ask about the content of the material you want to measure from research subjects or respondents (Notoatmodjo, 2012).

Mothers' knowledge can be obtained from several factors, both formal, such as education obtained from schools and non-formal, which mothers can obtain from posyandu, PKK,

and community health education activities (Notoatmodjo, 2012).

Education and information factors play an important role in acquiring knowledge, the higher a person's education, the easier it is to receive information so that the more knowledge they have. Likewise in terms of information, the more often someone gets information, the more that person's knowledge will increase.

Nutritional knowledge is the understanding and information an individual has about food and its nutrients and how they affect health. According to health behavior theory, knowledge is one of the important factors that influences a person's behavior in choosing healthy food. Mothers who have good nutritional knowledge tend to provide healthier food to their children, which has a positive impact on children's nutritional status and health.

Someone who has a high level of education will understand and understand more things than someone who has a lower education. This is evident from the respondents who answered the questionnaire, who had high knowledge, most of whom were respondents with a high school education, namely 49.3% (34 respondents). Respondents with high nutritional knowledge, apart from gaining knowledge about MP-ASI from formal education, have also received counseling from health workers at posyandu and have received information about MP-ASI from television, radio and print media.

The mother's knowledge about good nutrition will help the mother, especially in fulfilling nutritional substances in providing daily food, because with this the mother will know the pattern of providing nutritional food to toddlers and families so that nutritional needs for toddlers and families will be fulfilled.

2. Practice of Giving MP-ASI to Toddlers Aged 6-12 Months at BPM Ernah Kebon Kopi Cimahi

Practices are formed by the experience of individual interactions with the environment, especially those involving knowledge and attitudes towards an object. The practice of providing good and appropriate MP-ASI, especially for children aged 6-12 months, really supports the achievement of good nutritional status for children because children receive food according to their needs.

Many factors influence mothers' practices in feeding children under five, including knowledge, attitudes and characteristics of mothers which include age, education, number of family members, income, socio-culture and beliefs based on previous theoretical studies.

Research conducted by Rahayu et al. (2021) at BPM Ernah Kebon Kopi Cimahi shows that the majority of mothers give MP-ASI at the right age, namely 6 months. However, the quality and quantity of MP-ASI provided often does not meet the recommended nutritional standards. Many mothers give instant food or food that does not vary, so it does not meet the

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nutritional needs of toddlers optimally. The results of this research emphasize the importance of education and assistance to mothers regarding the selection and provision of MP-ASI in accordance with balanced nutrition guidelines.

The practice of providing MP-ASI at the Mlati Community Health Center, Yogyakarta, as revealed by Nugroho et al. (2021), shows that many mothers still lack knowledge and skills in preparing appropriate MP-ASI. The research results showed that some mothers gave MP-ASI that was too liquid and low in energy, so it did not meet the energy and nutritional needs of toddlers. Intervention in the form of practical training on preparing nutritious and safe MP-ASI is very necessary.

The results of research on the practice of giving MP-ASI showed that of the 69 respondents, 41 respondents (59.4%) had practiced giving MP-ASI to their children well. This can be caused by several factors, including the mother's knowledge obtained from various information and experiences, support and assistance from family members and the availability of food at the household level and the mother's characteristics.

3. The relationship between maternal nutritional knowledge and the practice of giving MP-ASI to toddlers aged 6-12 months at BPM Ernah Kebon Kopi Cimahi

The World Health Organization recommends exclusive breastfeeding until the baby is 6 months old, after that, MP-ASI should be introduced and breastfeeding continued until the baby is 2 years old. The quality of MP-ASI given to babies is determined by many factors, including food availability at the household level and maternal factors in giving MP-ASI to their babies and one of them is the mother's knowledge of nutrition and the practice of giving MP-ASI.

The results of the study were analyzed using Chi-square with $p < 0.05$, showing that there was a relationship between maternal nutritional knowledge and the practice of giving MP-ASI. According to Notoatmodjo (2012), theoretically knowledge will determine a person's behavior or actions. The higher a person's knowledge, the better the attitudes and behavior they have. Attitudes and behavior are also influenced by factors including personal experiences gained such as viewing, reading from print media and training or practice from other people.

The research results of Sudyanto et al (2003) in Pratiwi, Atika (2009) show that the knowledge and sources of information obtained by mothers about MP-ASI will influence the pattern of giving MP-ASI to babies. This is in line with the results of research by Mulyati (2000) that giving MP-ASI to babies is greatly influenced by the mother's knowledge and practice in giving MP-ASI.

Mothers' knowledge about MP-ASI also greatly influences the practice of giving MP-ASI for the first time to their children. Some mothers have given food other than breast milk to their babies before the age of 6 months, with different

amounts, frequencies, textures and types of food ingredients as well as feeding methods.

The research results of Mubin, M. Fathkul, et al (2008) stated that the mother's level of knowledge had a positive relationship with the baby's age when he first received MP-ASI. The higher the mother's level of knowledge, the more appropriate the age for giving MP-ASI to babies, and the lower the mother's knowledge level, the earlier the age for giving MP-ASI.

A mother's knowledge is needed in caring for her child, in terms of providing and serving food so that a child does not suffer from malnutrition (Suharjo, 2010). Mothers who have sufficient nutritional knowledge will have more information related to providing good nutrition for toddlers and of course this will have an influence on the process of food management practices in their homes from preparation to distribution to each member of the household, especially to their toddlers, compared to mothers who have knowledge about malnutrition. Thus, mothers who have high knowledge will influence the practice of providing MP-ASI so that it is hoped that it will have an effect on improving the nutritional status of their toddlers.

Based on the research results, there were respondents who had high nutritional knowledge but did not practice giving MP-ASI well. This is caused by several factors, including a lack of family support in providing MP-ASI to their children. Some respondents still live with other families such as grandparents and other relatives.

Based on the theory of Green, Lawrence (1991), grandparents and siblings who influence mothers' practices in feeding toddlers are included in the reinforcing factors, namely factors that strengthen changes in behavior caused by the people around them. Traditional factors in society are included in the basic facilitation factors (predisposing factors), namely the first factor that influences mothers' behavior in feeding toddlers.

CONCLUSION

1. Most mothers have a high level of nutritional knowledge.
2. The practice of giving MP-ASI to toddlers aged 6-12 months has been carried out well.
3. There is a relationship between maternal nutritional knowledge and the practice of giving MP-ASI to toddlers aged 6-12 months BPM Ernah Kebon Kopi Cimahi.

REFERENCES

- I. Aliyatun, Siti. 2003. Analysis of factors influencing mothers' practices in providing food for under-nourished children under five in the Bargas Health Center area, Semarang Regency, 2002. Postgraduate program thesis. Diponegoro University Semarang.
- II. Anonymous. 2014. Children's Diet Guide. 3rd Edition. Jakarta; Faculty of Medicine, University of Indonesia.

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- III. Arikunto, S. 2006. Research Procedures for a Practical Approach. Jakarta; Rineka Cipta.
- IV. Asmaini. 2013. Factors Associated with Providing Complementary Feeding for Breast Milk (MP-ASI) in Babies Aged 6-12 Months with the Occurrence of Diarrhea BPM Ernah Kebon Kopi Cimahi Kopelma Banda Aceh. Journal of Scientific Writing D III Midwifery. STIKes U'Budiyah Banda Aceh.
- V. Barasi, Mary E. At a Glance at Nutritional Science. Jakarta. Erlangga.
- VI. Republic of Indonesia Department of Health. Directorate General of Public Health Development. 2006. General Guidelines for Providing Local Complementary Food for Breast Milk (MP-ASI) in 2006. Jakarta: Indonesian Ministry of Health.
- VII. Fisher, Elvina, et al. Relationship between Mother's Level of Knowledge About Nutrition and Nutritional Status of Toddlers in Sioban Village, Mentawai Islands Regency. Biology Education Study Program Student e-journal. 2012; 1(1). Available URL: <http://jurnal.stkip-pgr-sumbar.ac.id/mhsbio.php/bio20121/article/view/95>
- VIII. Green. W. Lawrence. 1991. Health Promotion Planning an Educational and Environmental Approach. Second Edition, Mayfield Publishing Company.
- IX. Kartika, Dewi R, et al. 2010. Relationship between patterns of providing complementary food for breast milk (MP-ASI) and nutritional status in toddlers aged 6-12 months in Kaliori Village, Kalibagor District, Banyumas Regency. Midwifery Scientific Journal, Vol. 1 No. 1 December 2010 Edition.
- X. Indonesian Ministry of Health. 2010. Food Improvement Strategy and Infants and Children. Indonesian Ministry of Health.
- XI. Indonesian Ministry of Health. 2011. Complementary Food Counseling Training for Breast Milk (MP-ASI). Indonesian Ministry of Health.
- XII. Indonesian Ministry of Health. 2013. Basic Health Research. Health Research and Development Agency.
- XIII. Indonesian Ministry of Health, 2014. Infant and Child Feeding Counseling Module (IYCF). Indonesian Ministry of Health.
- XIV. Indonesian Ministry of Health. 2014. Guide to Implementing Infant and Child Feeding Counseling Training. Jakarta; Directorate of Nutrition Development.
- XV. Indonesian Ministry of Health. 2014. Handbook of Nutrition Care in Community Health Centers. Indonesian Ministry of Health.
- XVI. Krisnatuti, D and Yenrina, R. 2008. Preparing complementary foods for breast milk. Jakarta: Puspa Swara.
- XVII. Kurniasih, Dedeh, et al. 2010. Healthy & Fit Thanks to Balanced Nutrition. Jakarta : PT. Kompas Gramedia
- XVIII. Lubis, Ritayani. 2008. The Relationship between Mother's Parenting Patterns and the Nutritional Status of Toddlers in the Working Area of Pantai Cermin Health Center, Tanjung Pura District, Langkat Regency. Thesis. Faculty of Public Health. University of Northern Sumatra. Available URL: <http://www.fkm.unsri.ac.id>
- XIX. Mubin, M. Fathkul, et al. 2008. Factors Associated with the Age a Baby First Gets MP-ASI BPM Ernah Kebon Kopi Cimahi Tambak Aji Semarang. Journal of Nursing ; 2(1) : 24 – 34.
- XX. Notoatmodjo, Soekidjo. 2012. Health Research Methodology. Jakarta : Rineka Cipta.
- XXI. Notoatmodjo, Soekidjo. 2012. Health Promotion and Health Behavior. Revised Edition. Jakarta : Rineka Cipta.
- XXII. Nurmaliani, et al. 2010. Description of Mothers' Level of Knowledge and Providing Complementary Food for Breast Milk to Children Aged 6-24 Months in Kuto Batu Village, Palembang City. Journal of Public Health Sciences; 1 (02). Pp. 97-104. Available
- XXIII. Padang, Asdan. 2008. Analysis of Factors that Influence Mothers in Providing Early MP-ASI in Pandan District, Central Tapanuli Regency, 2007. Thesis: Postgraduate. University of North Sumatra Medan.
- XXIV. Pratiwi, Atika. 2009. Relationship between Knowledge and Mother's Behavior Regarding Giving MP-ASI to Toddlers Aged 6-24 Months at Posyandu Tlangu Hamlet, Bulan Village, Wonosari District, Klaten. Available URL: <http://diglib.uns.ac.id>.
- XXV. Saxena, Vartika Dr and Dr. Praveer Kumar. 2014. Complementary Feeding Practices in Rural Communities: A Study From Block Doiwala District Dehradun. Indian Journal of Basic and Applied Medical Research : Vol 3, Issue-2. P 358-363
- XXVI. Suhardjo. 2010. Feeding Babies and Children. 10th printing. Yogyakarta: Kanisius.
- XXVII. Sujarweni, V. Wiratna. 2014. Midwifery Research Guide Using SPSS. Yogyakarta: Pustaka Baru Press.
- XXVIII. World Health Organization. 2006. Facilitator Guide. The Community Infant and Young Child Feeding Counseling Package.
- XXIX. World Health Organization. 2002. Complementary Feeding: Summary of Guiding Principles. Report of

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the Global Consultation, 10–13 December 2001.
Geneva, Switzerland: World Health Organization.

XXX. Winarno. 2002. Food Chemistry and Nutrition.
Jakarta: Gramedia Pustaka Utama.